

Table S4

Expression	Intersections	Degree	Observed Overlap	Expected Overlap	FE	P.value	pAdj
Upregulated	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecastea</i> <i>uxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	5	23	6.42E-06	3582789.209	4.76E-145	1.90E-144
Upregulated	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecastea</i> <i>uxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	6	16	1.05E-07	152576607	5.02E-127	1.00E-126
Upregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i> & <i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecastea</i> <i>uxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	8	0	5.53E-13	0	1	1
Upregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i>	2	0	0.10081307 8	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i> & <i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecastea</i> <i>uxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	8	0	0	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Bassiana duperreyi</i> & <i>Lampropholis guichenoti</i>	2	0	0	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus coventryi</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecastea</i> <i>uxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	6	0	1.12E-10	0	1	1
Downregulated	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i> & <i>Niveoscincus ocellatus</i> & <i>Pseudemoia entrecastea</i> <i>uxii</i> & <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> & <i>Rhizoprionodon taylori</i>	5	0	4.02E-08	0	1	1